

Principles of Organizing and Conducting Extracurricular Work in a Foreign Language in Higher Education

Gulbahor Makhdievna Mansurova¹

¹ Senior teacher of the Department of Foreign Languages, Karshi engineering – economics institute

Abstract:

It is known that the language material studied in class is usually not used in the daily practice of students, and it is extracurricular work that can complement the academic work, help students consolidate and apply the knowledge they have acquired, and broaden their horizons. The article emphasizes that extracurricular work in a foreign language is an integral part of teaching, studying and developing the personality of a foreign language. Extracurricular work helps to more successfully solve the problems of the educational process: it promotes practical mastery of speech activity, increases the language stock of students, improves pronunciation, and stimulates their intellectual and linguistic activity in general.

Keywords: extracurricular work, linguistic activity, foreign language, students' cognitive interests.

Introduction:

At present, in modern higher education we are convinced that the systematization of theoretical and practical experience of extracurricular work is an integral and important part of the pedagogical process. Thanks to extracurricular work in a foreign language, students' cognitive interests deepen, social and cognitive motives for educational activity develop, the development of the individual, especially his creative potential, is stimulated, horizons, erudition and emotional-value attitude to the world and to oneself are significantly expanded [2, 252].

The functioning of the system of extracurricular work in a foreign language is based on a number of principles and specific requirements that determine the content, forms, methods, direction of pedagogical influence on the individual, the nature of the connection of individual elements of the

system. The principles of extracurricular work in a foreign language meet the goals and objectives of all extracurricular educational activities in a foreign language and illustrate the essence of the pedagogical activity of the teacher. The pedagogical process at the university involves close interaction of the teacher with the student. The creativity of the teacher is a necessary condition for the existence of the pedagogical process, and is considered as co-creation of teachers and students, joint activity or cooperation, involvement in a common cause, the possibility and necessity of exchanging experience between the teacher and the student [3].

Discussions:

The formation of the creative personality of the student involves his inclusion in various types and forms of activity. Training as a process of direct and indirect interaction of the teacher and students unfolds on a certain content. The content of training is a kind of product of co-creation of the teacher and students. At the stage of co-creation, learning becomes a process of business communication between equal and equivalent partners, and it is important for the student to be aware of his or her role in learning, as this activates the motivation for learning. Various forms of extracurricular work contribute to the involvement of teachers and students in co-creation [1, 152].

Extracurricular work is based on the following principles:

1. Connecting learning with life. The implementation of this principle allows for a close connection between extracurricular work on a foreign language and the living conditions and activities of students. The main conditions for implementing this principle are the following: systematic familiarization of students with current events in the life of our country and abroad; widespread use of local history material; meetings with people who use a foreign language in their professional activities.
2. Communicative activity of students.
3. A prerequisite for higher communicative activity of students in extracurricular work is the ability to choose the most interesting and accessible type of activity: correspondence with foreign colleagues, reading books in the language being studied, development of oral speech skills in scientific circle classes, etc. Not only the diversity of activities, but also their content is of great importance for stimulating communicative activity. The use of relevant authentic materials, their educational value and entertainment value cause the need for communication, improve its quality.
4. The principle of taking into account the level of language proficiency of students and the continuity of extracurricular work with foreign language classes. In extracurricular work, as well as in classes, it is necessary to achieve conscious application of knowledge, skills and abilities. The formation of interest in foreign language activities largely depends on the understanding of the content of the material used, the readiness of students to include it in speech activity.
5. The principle of combining collective, group and individual forms of work. A skillful combination of collective, group and individual forms of work is based on good knowledge by teachers of the contingent of students, their interests, capabilities, plans. This allows you to optimally select partners, distribute their roles. Individual, group and collective activities should be organically combined with each other.
6. Interdisciplinary connections in the preparation and implementation of extracurricular work in a foreign language. In the implementation of interdisciplinary connections, one of the requirements of the systemic approach to the work carried out on the training and education of students is realized. Taking into account this requirement, extracurricular work on a foreign language is not carried out in isolation, but in close connection with other academic subjects.

The inclusion of legal material allows for a significant reduction in interdisciplinary barriers. In the process of implementing various interdisciplinary connections, students are convinced that they need not a mechanical sum of knowledge on various subjects, but their interconnected system, capable of dynamic restructuring, which is required by the specifics of their future professional activity [4].

The effectiveness and efficiency of extracurricular work depends on both the above principles and the following conditions: involvement of all students in the work, regardless of their level of knowledge; combination of students' initiative with the guiding role of the teacher; entertaining and novel content, forms and methods of work; aesthetics of all events; clear organization and careful preparation of all planned events; availability of target settings and prospects for activity; wide use of methods of pedagogical stimulation of students' activity; transparency [6].

All the above principles and conditions complement each other and together provide a targeted, consistent, systematic and, at the same time, multifaceted influence on the development of personality. According to their meaning, the following forms of extracurricular work in a foreign language are distinguished: competitive (contest, olympiad, quiz), mass media (wall newspaper, announcement, bulletin, oral magazine, exhibition-quiz), cultural and mass (evening-festive, evening-meeting with interesting people; evenings-chronicles in connection with significant events, etc.), political and mass (forum, festival, press conference).

Conclusion:

It can be concluded that extracurricular activities play an important role in teaching a foreign language. They solve two main problems: developing interest, deepening knowledge, improving skills and abilities in a given subject; organizing students' free time for the purpose of their general development and aesthetic education. Moreover, designed and organized extracurricular activities are an important component of the educational process. Extracurricular forms of work successfully solve the problem of increasing interest in learning languages, and cultivate love and respect for foreign languages.

References:

1. Buxorova MX, Mansurova GM, Eshmurodov UK. FORMATION OF STUDENTS COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*. 2021(2):152-4.
https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=73RuxO4AAAAJ&citation_for_view=73RuxO4AAAAJ:u-x6o8ySG0sC.
2. Bukharova, M. K., G. M. Mansurova, and N. T. Ishonkulova. "MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING THE GERMAN LANGUAGE AT UNIVERSITIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*,(11), 611-613." (2019): 252-257.
3. Dilnoza Buriyevna Nashirova. (2023). the Role of Collaboration Technology in Foreign Language Classes in Higher Education Institutions. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 42, 44–48. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1991>.
4. Eshmuradov Urol Khujanovich. (2023). THEMATIC PRESENTATION AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING ORAL SPEECH AT A UNIVERSITY. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(4), 1713–1721. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7871933>.
5. Mansurova Gulbakhor Makhdievna. (2023). NEW TECHNIQUES AND MEANS OF TEACHING FOREIGN VOCABULARY IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY*

RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 8.036, 12(05), 74–78. Retrieved from <https://gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/1764>.

6. Nashirova, D. B., & Nashirova, S. B. (2020). CONTEMPORARY TRENDS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING: ACHIEVEMENTS, CHALLENGES OF APPEARING DIFFERENT LEVELS OF KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS. *Modern Science*, (5-2), 233-235. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=4090895672142763099&hl=ru&as_sdt=2005&sciodt=0,5.
7. Горелик И.Ф. Внеурочная работа средствами иностранного языка. ИЯШ, 1986, №6.
8. Дубровин М.И. Мотивация при обучении иностранному языку и учебные материалы. ИЯШ, 1978, №5.
9. Мансурова, Г. (2023). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ НА УРОКЕ НЕМЕЦКОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi*, (6), 441-445. <https://research-edu.com/index.php/namdu/article/view/315>.